

**SPATIO-TEMPORAL ASSESSMENT OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY
IN CHHATRAPATI SAMBHAJINAGAR DISTRICT USING SAPRE AND
DESHPANDE'S WEIGHTED RANKING INDEX**

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Abstract:

There are notable regional differences in agricultural output due to the intricate interplay of physical, socioeconomic, and technical factors. The current study uses the Sapre and Deshpande modified ranking coefficient approach to evaluate agricultural production and efficiency in the Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar district for the years 2023–2024. Nine tehsils with a variety of agroclimatic conditions make up the research region, which is located in Maharashtra's Godavari basin. Secondary data was gathered from official sources, including government statistics records and the District Socio-Economic Review. Productivity was calculated using weighted average indices based on crop area and yield rankings for eight key crops. The findings show significant regional differences in agricultural productivity between tehsils. Due to a balanced cropping pattern and greater yields, Khuldabad (3.83) and Kannad (3.85), which occupy 21.77% of the land, demonstrate excellent productivity. Sillod (4.13) and Phulambri (4.31), which account for 22.60% of the total area, have a mixed crop pattern and mediocre yield. Conversely, Vaijapur (5.00), Chh. Sambhajnagar (5.20), Gangapur (5.52), Soegaon (5.74), and Paithan (5.88), which account for 22.22% of the region, exhibit poor productivity as a result of the predominance of low-yield crops and inefficient land management. While cotton and sugarcane occupy enormous areas with poor yields, crops like maize, pulses, and oilseeds have comparatively better productivity. The study concludes that crop composition and resource use have a major role in the region's agricultural productivity.

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Keywords: Agricultural Productivity, Crop Pattern, Land Utilization, Productivity Index,

1. Introduction

Numerous interconnected factors influence agricultural productivity, including socioeconomic factors like landholding size, tenancy systems, occupational structure, and literacy

levels; physical factors like relief, altitude, climate, and soil conditions; and technical inputs like irrigation, chemical fertilizer use, high-yielding seed varieties, and mechanization. Significant regional and temporal variations in agricultural productivity result from these factors (Munir, 1995). Agricultural productivity has been interpreted by academics from a variety of fields, including geography, agronomy, agriculture, and economics, according to their respective goals and viewpoints. Because of this, it is seen as a dynamic term that varies based on social, technical, and environmental factors. The main industry in India and the foundation of the country's economy is agriculture. It has been essential to both the advancement of civilization and the population's social standing. Agriculture shows a great deal of variability in its methods and results since it is heavily reliant on climatic conditions, technical inputs, and infrastructure support. Agricultural efficiency is one of the most crucial ideas among the many approaches that have been devised to gauge agricultural progress. It facilitates comprehension of the efficient use of land resources in the industrial process. Nearly 60% of Indians rely on agriculture for their livelihood in addition to being the primary source of food.

In addition to making a substantial contribution to the GDP and general economy, it directly affects health, poverty alleviation, and food and nutritional security. India's planting patterns and agricultural methods have changed significantly throughout time, resulting in differences in production levels. In particular, agricultural efficiency assesses a piece of land's productivity by looking at its capacity, fertility, and production levels. Additionally, it is essential for monitoring and planning the use of agricultural land in the future.

2. Review of Literature

According to Stamp (1952), several scholars have attempted to investigate agricultural output by suggesting and improving different tactics. In order to assess agricultural production globally, Shafi (1960) selected many countries and a few important crops. The areal unit and ranking coefficient were computed. According to Khusro's (1964) research, many others evaluated agricultural productivity in terms of grain equivalents per population. calculating output in relation to input or output-input ratio, as well as measuring farming profitability in terms of the return for the entire amount of human effort or paid-out expenditures in proportion to the production. Productivity is calculated by assigning weight to the ranking order of production per unit area with the percentage share under each crop, according to Sapre-Deshpande (1964) and Bhatia (1967). Buck (1967) computed the agricultural efficiency of Uttar Pradesh using his approach. According to Cantor's (1967) research, furrow irrigation is frequently employed because it may be applied to a variety of soil types and land slopes.

It may be utilized with both large and small streams of irrigated water. Singh (1975) asserts that the land in developing countries is too limited to sustain any expansion in the cultivated area,

and the increasing population pressure on existing land compels geographers and agricultural scientists to think about measures to boost agricultural production. The productivity value per unit area was determined in monetary terms by Hussain (1976). The linked yield and concentration index ranking coefficient technique, created by Jasbir Singh in 1976, is employed; it gives the ranking of the several crops he also studied and the per hectare yield area occupied the proper weight.

3. Objective

1. To analyze the level of agricultural productivity across different tehsils of Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar district for the year 2023–24.
2. To measure agricultural efficiency using the weighted average index method based on crop area and productivity.
3. To classify tehsils into high, moderate, and low productivity regions and examine regional variations in agricultural performance.

Figure No. 01

5. Methodology

The primary objective of this research is to assess the district's agricultural output index for the years 2023–2024. To do this, eight of the primary crops farmed in the region were chosen for in-depth analysis. The data utilized in this study came from secondary sources. The particular sources of the data used for the study were the district's socioeconomic overview, the Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar District Handbook, and the Department of Economics and Statistics. These materials give a solid foundation for the research by offering in-depth studies of the productivity and agricultural performance of the selected crops. This approach aims to produce an accurate assessment of the district's agricultural output throughout the specified period. Kendall's "ranking coefficient" method was somewhat modified in 1964 by V.D. Deshpande and S.G. Sapre. In place of the "simple average of ranks," "weighted average rankings" were employed. The percentage of farmland devoted to each crop is displayed in the weighted rankings of the different crops. The productivity index may be computed using the following formula:

$$\text{Weighted Average of Ranks} = \frac{\sum(R \times A)}{\sum A}$$

Whereas,

R = Ranking of Yield of Individual Crops

A = Crop Land Share in %

6. Result and Discussion

The current study's findings demonstrate notable differences in agricultural production amongst the region's several tehsils in 2023–2024. Crop-wise area, productivity, and ranking have all been considered while calculating the weighted average index using the Sapre and Deshpande technique. Major crops that are crucial to the region's agricultural economy, including wheat, maize, pulses, cotton, oilseeds, and sugarcane, are included in the research. The results show that tehsils differ in terms of yield levels, land use, and cropping patterns. The tehsils have been divided into regions with high, moderate, and poor productivity based on the weighted average index values. This categorization aids in comprehending.

Table No. 01: Comparative Analysis of Crop Productivity and Weighted Ranking in Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar (2023–24)

Tehsils	Kannad				Soesgaon				Sillood						
	Area	Productivity	Rank	Area %	R*A	Area	Productivity	Rank	Area %	R*A	Area	Productivity	Rank	Area %	R*A
Wheat	20959	1799.9	4	13.93	55.74	1994	1374.7	3	3.82	11.46	10384	1841.8	3	7.79	23.36
Jowar	2903	697.58	6	1.93	11.58	2217	995	5	4.25	21.23	837	1054.4	5	0.63	3.14
Bajra	2293	1046.7	5	1.52	7.62	845	578.29	6	1.62	9.71	1025	713.3	6	0.77	4.61
Maize	54120	2599	1	35.98	35.98	5494	1356.8	4	10.52	42.08	43973	1549.2	4	32.97	131.87
Pulses	15565	1800.68	3	10.35	31.04	3206	2098.41	1	6.14	6.14	26216	2586.28	1	19.66	19.66
Sugarcane	3598	62	8	2.39	19.14	8	0	0	0.02	0.00	280	52	8	0.21	1.68
Cotton	47099	198.47	7	31.31	219.18	35062	113.07	7	67.14	469.99	40853	348.29	7	30.63	214.41
Oilseeds	3881	1972.82	2	2.58	5.16	3395	1662.05	2	6.50	13.00	9810	2545.5	2	7.36	14.71
	150418			100.00	385.44	52221			100.00	573.61	133378			100.00	413.43
	Weighted Average of Ranks				3.95	Weighted Average of Ranks				5.74	Weighted Average of Ranks				4.13

Source: Computed by Researcher

Table No. 02: Comparative Analysis of Crop Productivity and Weighted Ranking in Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar (2023–24)

Tehsils	Phulambri				Chh. Sambhajinagar				Khuldabad						
	Area	Productivity	Rank	Area %	R*A	Area	Productivity	Rank	Area %	R*A	Area	Productivity	Rank	Area %	R*A
Rice	5022	1942	4	7.69	30.78	3467	1334.5	4	3.96	15.85	4175	1497.8	4	8.95	35.78
Wheat	629	929.74	5	0.96	4.82	9787	1214.7	5	11.18	55.91	3237	772.86	5	6.94	34.68
Jowar	690	826.55	6	1.06	6.34	5438	543.15	6	6.21	37.28	945	657.97	6	2.02	12.15
Bajara	22525	2542.1	2	34.51	69.03	11713	1436.1	3	13.38	40.15	14908	2634.8	1	31.94	31.94
Maize	9221	1946.25	3	14.13	42.39	10662	1955.9	2	12.18	24.36	5756	1528.4	3	12.33	37.00
Pulses	615	56	8	0.94	7.54	470	53	8	0.54	4.30	822	52	8	1.76	14.09
Sugarcane	24923	234.78	7	38.19	267.31	42191	233.67	7	48.21	337.45	13517	211.01	7	28.96	202.73
Cotton	1641	4405.3	1	2.51	2.51	3793	2701.1	1	4.33	4.33	3312	1924.39	2	7.10	14.19
	65266			100.00	430.71	87521			100.00	519.63	46672			100.00	382.56
	Weighted Average of Ranks				4.31	Weighted Average of Ranks				5.20	Weighted Average of Ranks				3.83

Source: Computed by Researcher

Table No. 03: Comparative Analysis of Crop Productivity and Weighted Ranking in Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar (2023–24)

Tehsils	Vaijapur					Gangapur					Paithan				
	Area	Productivity	Rank	Area %	R*A	Area	Productivity	Rank	Area %	R*A	Area	Productivity	Rank	Area %	R*A
Rice	7667	1874.5	2	4.75	9.49	8868	2015.5	1	7.39	7.39	6249	1769.1	2	6.45	12.89
Wheat	6280	979.74	5	3.89	19.44	7798	1035.8	5	6.50	32.48	5852	714.16	5	6.04	30.19
Jowar	3760	659.71	6	2.33	13.97	2245	659.6	6	1.87	11.22	4678	539.99	6	4.83	28.96
Bajara	47648	1422.6	4	29.50	117.98	15837	1482.9	4	13.19	52.78	962	1208.7	4	0.99	3.97
Maize	17134	1887.7	1	10.61	10.61	11288	2005.9	2	9.40	18.81	12299	1554.4	3	12.69	38.06
Pulses	5960	48	8	3.69	29.52	6470	68	8	5.39	43.12	8977	72	8	9.26	74.09
Sugarcane	65986	144.76	7	40.85	285.93	65317	166.26	7	54.42	380.93	54962	151.04	7	56.70	396.90
Cotton	7106	1708.88	3	4.40	13.20	2204	1574.63	3	1.84	5.51	2956	4003.2	1	3.05	3.05
	161541			100.00	500.13	120027			100.00	552.24	96935			100.00	588.10
	Weighted Average of Ranks					Weighted Average of Ranks					Weighted Average of Ranks				
	5.00					5.52					5.88				

Source: Computed by Researcher

The crop-wise distribution of acreage and production across various tehsils is shown in detail in the following table, which clearly illustrates regional differences in agricultural performance. The greatest agricultural lands are found in Kannad and Vaijapur, where maize and cotton predominate. Although maize is very productive, cotton and sugarcane produce relatively little. Despite having a low area coverage, Sillod and Khuldabad show superior productive performance, particularly in pulses, maize, and oilseeds, demonstrating effective land usage. On the other hand, Soegaon's mediocre yield and very small cultivated area indicate a low level of agricultural intensity. Chh and Phulambri. Sambhajinagar has a mixed pattern, with high-yielding crops like oilseeds and maize coexisting alongside lower-yielding cotton and sugarcane on a sizable percentage of the area, which reduces overall efficiency. Large tracts of cotton and sugarcane are grown in Gangapur and Paithan, although their yield is still poor, indicating less effective farming methods. While sugarcane and cotton constantly exhibit lower production while occupying a significant amount of land, maize, pulses, and oilseeds typically record better productivity across all tehsils. Overall, the data shows that crop productivity has a major role in agricultural performance and that tehsils with a better mix of high-yielding crops use their land more efficiently.

Table No. 04: Weighted Average Index 2023-24

Sr.	Name of Tehsils	Weighted Average Index
1	Kannad	3.85
2	Soegaon	5.74
3	Sillod	4.13
4	Phulambri	4.31
5	Chh. Sambhajinagar	5.20
6	Khuldabad	3.83
7	Vaijapur	5.00
8	Gangapur	5.52
9	Paithan	5.88

Source: Computed by Researcher

The Weighted Average Index for 2023–2024 by tehsil shows significant differences in agricultural productivity throughout the research region. more index values show comparatively lesser efficiency, whereas lower ones show more efficiency. The tehsils with the best agricultural

efficiency are Khuldabad (3.83) and Kannad (3.85), followed by Sillod (4.13) and Phulambri (4.31), where a comparatively balanced mix of crop area and production leads to improved performance. Vaijapur (5.00) and Chh. Sambhajinagar (5.20), on the other hand, have modest efficiency levels, suggesting an imbalance between crop yield and area allocation. Soegaon (5.74), Gangapur (5.52), and Paithan (5.88) are the least efficient tehsils; higher index values indicate that a greater percentage of cultivated land is planted with low-productivity crops or that crop yields are relatively lower.

Table No. 05

Agriculture Productivity Regions based on Sapre and Deshpande Index

Sr. No.	Index Value	Level of Productivity	No. of Tehsils	Tehsils	% of Area
1	Below 3.85	High	02	Khuldabad (3.83) and Kannad (3.85)	21.77
2	3.86 to 4.31	Moderate	02	Sillod (4.13) and Phulambri (4.31)	22.60
3	Above 4.32	Low		Vaijapur (5.00), Chh. Sambhajinagar (5.20), Gangapur (5.20), Soegaon (5.74) and Paithan (5.88)	22.22

Source: Computed by Researcher

Figure No. 02

6.1 High Productivity Regions (Index Value Below 3.85):

When the index value is less than 3.85, the high productivity region denotes the study region's most agriculturally efficient areas. Together, Khuldabad (3.83) and Kannad (3.85) make up 21.77 percent of the entire geographic area. Because crop area and production are well combined, these tehsils exhibit a high degree of agricultural efficiency. The comparatively lower index values show that more land is used for high-yielding crops and that main crop productivity levels are much higher than in other areas. In these regions, crops including oilseeds, pulses, and maize have a good impact on overall agricultural performance. Productivity is further increased by a balanced cropping plan, improved use of agricultural inputs, and advantageous socioeconomic and physical circumstances. These areas are better developed in terms of agricultural growth as they exhibit effective farming methods and appropriate land use. All things considered, the high productivity areas are vital to the study area's agricultural economy and may be used as models to raise production in other, less productive areas.

6.2 Moderate Productivity Regions (Index Value 3.86 to 4.31):

Tehsils with average agricultural efficiency (index values ranging from 3.86 to 4.31) are included in the moderate productivity area. Sillod (4.13) and Phulambri (4.31), which together make up 22.60 percent of the total area, are included in this group. Although the efficiency is not as great as in the best-performing areas, these tehsils show a reasonably balanced connection between crop area and productivity. Overall performance is mediocre when both high-yielding and low-yielding crops are present. Although crops like maize, oilseeds, and pulses are beneficial in these regions, a sizable portion of the land is also used for crops with comparatively lower productivity, which has an impact on the index score as a whole. Productivity levels are further influenced by differences in planting patterns, irrigation infrastructure, and the usage of contemporary agricultural inputs. Even if the agricultural growth in these areas is excellent, there is still room for progress through improved crop planning, the use of cutting-edge methods, and effective resource management.

6.3 Low Productivity Regions (Index Value Above 4.32):

Tehsils with index values over 4.32 that have relatively low agricultural efficiency are included in the low productivity area. Together, Vaijapur (5.00), Chh. Sambhajinagar (5.20), Gangapur (5.52), Soegaon (5.74), and Paithan (5.88) make up 22.22 percent of the total area. Higher index values, which show an imbalance between agricultural acreage and production, are characteristic of these tehsils. Low-yielding or inconsistently productive crops, such sugarcane and

pulses, occupy a large percentage of agricultural land in these areas, negatively impacting overall efficiency. Lower production levels are also caused by irregular cropping patterns, a lack of utilization of contemporary agricultural inputs, and potential limitations with regard to irrigation, soil quality, and climate. These areas demonstrate the need for better crop planning, enhanced agricultural techniques, and a greater uptake of contemporary technology and high-yielding cultivars. All things considered, the low production areas show the difficulties in attaining effective agricultural growth and necessitate focused interventions for improvement.

7. Conclusion

The Weighted Average Index values in the current study show notable geographical differences in agricultural productivity among the tehsils. The high productivity group includes tehsils like Khuldabad (3.83) and Kannad (3.85), which account for 21.77 percent of the total area and show improved agricultural yield and effective land use. Sillod (4.13) and Phulambri (4.31), which account for 22.60 percent of the land and have index values between 3.86 and 4.31, are regions of moderate productivity where agricultural performance is balanced but subpar. Conversely, Vaijapur (5.00), Chh. Sambhajinagar (5.20), Gangapur (5.52), Soegaon (5.74), and Paithan (5.88) comprise 22.22 percent of the area and are classified as low productivity locations. This indicates reduced efficiency because of uneven cropping patterns and lower yields. Additionally, the study shows that while cotton and sugarcane occupy greater areas with relatively lower production, the productivity of crops like maize, oilseeds, and pulses is substantially higher, improving index values. Overall, the results highlight that the balance between crop area and productivity has a significant impact on agricultural efficiency, and that restoring this balance is crucial to boosting agricultural growth in the area.

8. Reference

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